

The Role of Physical Education and Sports in the Daily Activities of Students Who are Studying in Pedagogy

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Abstract. *Based on the research, the article reveals the role of physical culture and sports in the daily activities of students of pedagogical directions. It has been established that students who do not engage in physical culture or sports have indicators characterizing physical capabilities at a lower level than athletes engaged in sports, and these indicators decrease even more both at the end of the academic year and during the transition from course to course.*

Key words: *Student, pedagogy, education, physical opportunity, physical education, sports, intellectual work.*

Relevance. From the results of visual and formal observations, it can be seen that the daily activities of most students studying in various pedagogical educational fields are controlled by intellectual processes (classroom classes, computer work, searching for necessary information on Internet sites, working in the library, creative work at home, etc.). being at the very top. In them, the amount of daily physical activity is extremely limited, and it turned out that 70.0-78.9% of students do not engage in physical education, wellness classes or sports sections, which are conducted independently or in an organized team. 30-hour physical education classes, which are held in the 1st semester of the 1st year according to the curriculum, will not only "fail" to strengthen the health of students, will not develop general physical qualities, but also will not allow them to form professional and practical action skills.

It is known from a number of sources that following a healthy lifestyle, which includes such activities as nutrition, sleep, preparation of the body during physical exercises or regular physical activity, as a daily need, not only strengthens health, intensively forms physical and psycho-functional capabilities, but also increases the ability to creatively and intellectually work. [N.E.Vetkov, 2016, pp. 126-141; I.Y.Gorskaya, 2014, p. 63; E.V.Matukhno, 2013, 97 p.; A.D.Korbina, 2014, pp.101-105; A.O.Egorichev, 2020, pp. 65-80; K.V.Buchenkov, 2019, 25 p.]

The purpose of the study is to study the growth rate of physical abilities of future teachers-students who are engaged and not engaged in physical education and sports.

Research methods and its organization. The study used traditional pedagogical tests designed to assess indicators of general physical fitness. The research was conducted from January 2018 to July 2019, 132 students studying in the specialty "mathematics" and 129 students studying in the direction of "Physics" in grades 1-4 of Andijan State University took part in them.

The studies were conducted before and after 30-hour physical education classes in the 1st year, including at the beginning and end of the academic year of each course.

The results of the study and their discussion. The results of the study showed that the interval from long jumps to 30-hour physical education classes, which are held in the 1st semester of the 1st year

according to the plan, for students of the "mathematical" direction is 217.5 ± 5.08 cm ni, 219.7 ± 5.47 cm for "physical" students. if the number of these classes is 221.4 ± 6.06 cm, respectively, by the end of these classes. and 223.9 ± 6.73 cm. It was found that it had grown to.

Table-1. Dynamics of changes in physical abilities during 30-hour practical classes conducted during 1 semester for 1st year students studying in the fields of mathematical and physical education – $\bar{X} \pm \sigma$

Pedagogical tests	Before PE classes		After PE classes		Indicator difference	
	M n=36	Ph n=38	M n=33	Ph n=35	M	B
Jump from place to length (sm.)	217,5±5,08	219,7±5,47	221,4±6,06	223,9±6,73	003,9	004,2
Pull as much as possible on the turnstile (times)	7,6±1,13	8,1±1,17	8,9±1,26	9,2±1,35	1,3	1,1
Posture in a sitting position-bending the head towards the knee (sm)	17,7±3,06	18,2±3,14	15,5±2,37	16,8±2,57	2,2	1,1
100m. Running. (S.)	15,3±1,34	14,7±1,27	14,6±1,22	13,5±1,17	0,7	1,1
1000 m. Running (min/s.)	4,43±0,29	4,45±0,36	4,23±0,32	4,27±0,35	0,20	1,1

Note: M – Mathematics

Ph – Physics

The number of maximum possible turnstiles increased, respectively, from 7.6 ± 1.13 times to 8.9 ± 1.26 times for mathematics students and from 8.1 ± 1.17 times to 9.2 ± 1.35 times for physics students. In the sitting position, the angle of inclination of the trunk-head to the knee is 17.7 ± 3.08 cm from 15.5 ± 2.37 cm above and 18.2 ± 3.14 cm from 16.8 ± 2.57 cm below. The running speed per 100m increased from 13.5 ± 1.17 to 15.3 ± 1.34 s, and from 13.5 ± 1.17 to 14.7 ± 1.27 s. The running speed per 1000 m increased from 4.43 ± 0.29 min/s to 4.23 ± 0.32 min/s and 4.45 ± 0.36 min/s from 4.27 ± 0.35 min/s. It was noticed that changed towards progression.

From the dynamics of these indicators, it can be seen that in both groups participating in the study, the indicators of the studied physical capabilities (explosive strength, flexor arm muscle strength, flexibility, dexterity, endurance) changed for the better by the end of 30-hour physical education classes. Alternatively, it was found that the indicators obtained before and after these 30-hour physical education classes for 1st year students, including the indicators recorded at the beginning of the academic year in the remaining 2, 3, 4 courses, had changed towards regression by the end of the academic year. For example, at the beginning of the school year, the distance from the place to the long jump for 1st year students was 219.8 ± 6.73 sm from 216.5 ± 5.52 sm. It was noticed that it decreased to. (Table 2)

For 2 meals, these indicators amounted to 218.4 ± 5.47 cm, respectively. from 2.15 ± 5.14 sm to 216.7 ± 5.15 sm in 3 sessions. from 214.3 ± 5.01 sm to 213.6 ± 4.57 sm in 4 sessions. from 210.5 ± 4.25 sm, it was found that it decreased to.

At the beginning of the school year, the average height was 217.1 cm. At the end of the school year - 214.2 sm down.

Table-2. The rate of development of physical abilities during the academic year for students of 1-4 courses studying in the field of mathematical education – $\bar{X} \pm \sigma$

Pedagogical tests	1 κ n=30	2 κ n=28	3 κ n=27	4 κ n=25	$\bar{X}$
Jump from place to length (sm.)	219,8±6,73 216,5±5,52	218,4±5,47 215,3±5,14	216,7±5,15 214,3±5,01	213,6±4,57 210,5±4,25	217,1 214,2
Pull as much as possible on the turnstile (times)	8,9±1,27 8,7±1,19	8,5±1,21 8,3±1,15	8,2±1,12 7,7±1,09	7,8±1,11 7,5±1,06	8,5 8,1
Posture in a sitting position-bending the head towards the knee (sm)	17,8±3,12 18,6±2,79	19,5±3,37 21,7±3,68	20,8±3,46 23,5±3,75	22,5±3,67 24,2±3,88	20,1 22,0
100m. Running. (S.)	13,7±1,39 14,4±1,63	14,3±1,42 15,7±1,45	14,8±1,47 16,1±1,79	15,5±1,77 16,9±1,75	14,6 15,8

**Note: up – at the beginning of the school year
down- at the end of the school year**

The number of maximum possible twists on the turnstile decreased, respectively, in 1 move – from 8.9±1.27 times to 8.7±1.19 times, in 2 moves – from 8.5±1.21 times to 8.3±1.15 times, in 3 moves - from 8.2±1.12 times to 7.7±1.09 times, in 3 moves - from 8.2±1.12 times to 7.7±1.09 times. 4 courses - from 7.8 ± 1.11 times to 7.5± 1.06 times.

It was noticed that the average figures decreased from 8.5 to 8.1 times.

The angle of flexion of the trunk-head to the knee in a sitting position for 1 reception is 17.8 ± 3.12 sm. from 18.6 ± 2.79 cm. to, for 2 receptions - 19.5 ± 3.37 sm. from 21.7 ± 3.68 sm. to, for 4 receptions – 22.5 ± 3.67 cm. from 24.2± 3.88 sm. elasticity is increased or impaired. At the beginning of the school year, the average was 20.1 cm. ni finished the school year with an increase of 22.0 sm.

100 m . Running speed in the 1st lap - 13.7 ± 1.39 s. from 14.4 ± 1.63 s. to, in the 2nd lap – 14.3 ± 1.42 s. from 15.7 ± 1.45 s. to, in the 3rd lap – 14.8 ± 1.47 s. from 16.1 ± 1.79 s. to, in the 4th lap - 15.5±1.77 s. compared with 16.9±1.75 s. was found to be sluggish. At the beginning of the school year, the average is 14.6 seconds. by the end of the school year, it will be 15.8 seconds. down.

It can be seen from the results of the above study, the indicators of physical abilities of future teachers-students of mathematics and physics changed from course to course, and towards the end of the academic year - in a negative direction. So, at the beginning of the 1st year, it can be assumed that students' physical abilities, formed to a certain extent, will fall even more at the end of the academic year and in subsequent courses they will experience more and more a decrease in physical activity, which will depend on "not having so much time" to exercise regularly, However, as noted above, purposeful physical education or sports, as is known, not only strengthen health, form physical and psycho-functional capabilities, but also increase the ability to mental work, they also improve the quality and efficiency of intellectual work.

It was noted that this opinion is to some extent confirmed by the results of research on students who practice a number of sports. In particular, for student volleyball players, the distance from the place to the long jump is 235.3±4.43 sm., 237.8 ±5.07 sm for student players. ni, 239.3±5.19 sm for students involved in mini-football.

The average figures are 237.1 cm in sports students.in for students who do not study, as noted by <url>, this figure is 215.6 cm. This is equivalent.

It was found that the number of possible jerks on the turnstile for volleyball students involved in mini-football was 10.3±1.27 times, for students - 12.3±1.54 times. While the average for students involved in sports was 11.5 times, for students not involved in sports, it was 8.3 times.

In the sitting position, the length of the trunk - the angle of inclination of the head to the knee - is 11.5 ± 1.35 cm for student volleyball players, 13.6 ± 2.07 cm for student players, 12.3 ± 1.54 sm for students involved in mini-football. fixed with. For students involved in sports, the average figures are 12.5 sm, for students not involved in sports - 20.4 sm. installed.

Running speeds of 100 and 1000 m. was also clearly higher among students involved in sports.

It is noteworthy that the majority of students involved in sports (74.3%) also admire the indicators of mastering subjects, confirming the idea noted above.

Conclusion. Based on a comparative analysis of the results of the study, it can be recognized that almost all average indicators reflecting the physical abilities of students who receive education in pedagogical areas and do not regularly engage in physical culture or sports were initially recorded (at the beginning of the school year) far from the norm. "healthy and mobile youth", although they were. At the same time, it is worth noting that the indicators of physical abilities of students who regularly engage in sports are relatively high, especially since the qualities of flexibility, speed and endurance are close to those of Razorback athletes. But it is also worth noting that for students, not only physical education or sports during daily activities are useful both for health promotion and for increasing the ability to mental work, it is also important to regularly develop professional and practical physical skills in the process of such training.

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